

Strategic Management Adoption and Performance of TransNzoia County, Kenya

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14716403>

Published Date: 22-January-2025

Abstract: The purpose of the study was to examine the effect of strategic management adoption on Performance of TransNzoia County. The study was guided by the following specific objectives as; to examine the influence of strategic planning adoption on Performance of TransNzoia County. The study used the following theories as resource based view and goal setting theory. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The target Population was all county directors from all the 13 departments in of TransNzoia County. Data collection instrument was structured questionnaire. Both primary and secondary data was collected. The researcher self-drop and pick the duly filled questionnaires. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of data collection instrument. Data was organised, coded, edited to bring a meaning. Data was be analysed and presented using the statistical package for social science SPSS version 24. Both descriptive and inferential statistics shall be done. Multiple regression was done to test the significant levels of one variable over the other. Analysis of variance was also be done. Based on the findings, the study concluded that strategic planning adoption has significant effect on Performance of TransNzoia County. The study came up with the following recommendations; the management of the county government should come up with Strategic plan that meets the county government's requirements in consideration and articulation of values and priorities reflecting the views expressed by all stakeholders involved in the process. The adoption process should involve the strategic vision, mission, goals and values of the organization. The finding will be of significant to the researchers, academicians, stakeholders and to the entire economy as a whole.

Keywords: Strategic Planning Option, Organisational Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

In view of the many challenges that business organizations are exposed to, it is imperative for them, both profit and non-profit organizations, to anticipate challenges, identify their strengths to meet anticipated challenges and take control of available opportunities to obtain maximum productivity. Will K. (2022) states that strategic management is the management of an organization's resources to achieve its goals and objectives. Strategic management adoption involve the art and science of formulating, implementing, and evaluating cross-functional decisions that enable an organization to achieve its objectives (Strickland, 2013). It is the formal process, or set of processes, used to determine the strategies (actions) for the organization. It focuses on many areas, including the integration of management, marketing, finance/accounting, production/operations, research and development and computer information systems (Massila et al.,2024). Strategy as practice perspective looks at strategy as something people do. Strategic practice is based on the common sense idea that we have to relate tactics to strategy and strategic goals. This involves asking what kind of choices organizations must make in order to be effective in the short term and at the same time take on this challenge (McKiernan, 2006).

In the world of competition and turbulent business environment, achieving operational performance in organizations is dependent on multiple factors which may be internal and external (Quinn & Hilmer, 2014). Massila et al., (2024) states that strategic management adoption refers to the process by which an organization integrates strategic management adoption

into its operations. This involves the systematic planning, monitoring, analysis, and assessment of all that is necessary for an organization to meet its objectives. Cherian et al (2021) observe that in the modern competitive business environment, organizations from one sector to another can utilize strategic resources in attaining long term and short term goals. Will K. (2022) states that strategic management is the management of an organization's resources to achieve its goals and objectives. Strategic management adoption involve the art and science of formulating, implementing, and evaluating cross-functional decisions that enable an organization to achieve its objectives (Strickland, 2013). It is the formal process, or set of processes, used to determine the strategies (actions) for the organization. It focuses on many areas, including the integration of management, marketing, finance/accounting, production/operations, research and development and computer information systems (McKiernan, 2006). Strategy as practice perspective looks at strategy as something people do. Strategic practice is based on the common sense idea that we have to relate tactics to strategy and strategic goals. This involves asking what kind of choices organizations must make in order to be effective in the short term and at the same time take on this challenge (McKiernan, 2006).

Fuertes et al (2020) revealed that processes required to achieve organizational goals in other to confront the challenges of strategic management includes environmental analysis, strategy formulation, modern strategy implementation, and effective human resources management. Similar practices are applied through strategic planning. Strategic management adoption consists of three basic elements, strategy formulation, implementation, evaluation and control (AlQutob et al (2020). It is within these three elements that strategic management adoption are manifested and is also described as the strategic management process (Ameen et al., 2020). The concept of organizational performance is core to businesses because the major objective of businesses is to make profits. Alsyof et al (2021) state that one of the important questions in business has been why some organizations succeed and why others fail and this has influenced a study on the drivers of organizational performance. Virtaneva et al (2021), asserts that for an organization to be successful it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization. Hassan and Jiang, (2021) highlight performance measurement as one of the tools which helps firms in monitoring performance, identifying the areas that need attention, enhancing motivation, improving communication and strengthening accountability.

Regionally, firm's performance requires strategic management adoption involving the art and science of formulating, implementing, and evaluating cross- functional decisions that enable an organization to achieve its objectives (Ekon & Bemnet, 2022;). According to Agrawal (2016), it is the formal process, or set of processes, used to determine the strategies (actions) for the organization. For organisational performance to be of quality, strategic management has to focus on many areas, including; the integration of management, marketing, finance/accounting, production/operations, research and development and computer information systems, hence; Strategy as practice for organisational performance perspective looks at strategy as something people do (AlDhaheri et al.,2023). Strategic practice is based on the common sense idea that we have to relate tactics to strategy and strategic goals (Nwanekezie, et al.,2022). This involves asking what kind of choices organizations must make in order to be effective in the short term and at the same time take on this challenge (Khalid et al., 2020). Slabbert, et al (2018) did a study on the role of Strategic management adoption on Organizational Performance of United Nations Development Programme in Mogadishu, Somalia. The findings revealed that there is a strong relationship between strategic management adoption and organisational performance.

Locally, strategic management adoption consists of four basic elements, strategic planning, implementation, evaluation and control (Yusuf et al., 2022). It is within these four elements that strategic management adoption are manifested and is also described as the strategic management process. Strategic leadership adoption is a component of strategic management adoption that involves provision of direction and leadership toward implementation of planned strategy. Strategy formulation is the development of long-range plans for the effective management of environmental opportunities and threats, in light of corporate strengths and weaknesses (Kanano, et al., 2021). It includes defining the corporate mission, specifying achievable objectives, developing strategies and setting policy guidelines.

Gure et al., (2018) states that strategic management adoption is and will always be the backbone of any organisation. According to Timothy et al.,(2021) strategic leadership adoptions challenges are the main concerns in many organisation. Simsek, et al.,(2015) states that strategic leaders include chief executive officers, company directors, and top managers, leading middle line managers and the wider organization workforce to deliver shareholder and stakeholder value. Strategic leaders are charged with critical choices to facilitate transfer of information, influence and resources with implications for organization performance (Simsek, Heavey & Fox, 2018). Nzuve and Nyaega (2012) opined that Performance management and improvement is at the heart of strategic management because a lot of strategic thinking is geared towards defining and

measuring performance. Awino (2011) asserts that for an organization to be successful it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization. Organizations create transformational leadership teams who have the knowledge, insight and experience to help organizations create a flexible, scalable and cost effective platform for delivering functional and business enabling processes (Kanano and Wanjira, 2021). Khalid and Nusari, (2020) indicate that improvement in Organisational performance is also informed by the need to grow and expand services, take advantage of opportunities or merely to implement new knowledge which can come up with action plans.

In many developing countries, the issue of firms performance is a challenge that needs to be addressed given the low quality of service provision and the pressing needs of the poor (Besley and Ghatak, 2007). Khalid et al., (2020) supports this view when he states that local councils in Malaysia continue to face pressure to improve their firms. The increased level of education of the population has led to a more vocal and more discerning citizenry that expects better services and accountability from its local government. Moreover, rapid industrialization and urbanization of countries have created a challenging environment for the local government (Hunt, 2021). Tamrakar (2010) affirms that in Nepal, public organisational performance has remained lower than what was targeted when Nepal announced delivery of public services to its people through a planned development effort. The USA is well known for its significant improvements in ensuring strategic management adoption in its devolved units which has seen an explosion in development of infrastructure for economic sustainability. The rural communities in the USA have grown to enviable levels and most of the devolved units are deemed semi or partially autonomous (Kelegama, 2011). Ever since the introduction of counties in Latin America development planners and academic scholars have underlined the role co-operatives should and do play in stepping-up development. This official and popular support for devolution strengthening has been omnipresent and has received a prominent place in such diverse economic political approaches have been witnessed (Khalid et al., 2020).

Regionally, the problem of Organisational performance due to poor strategic management adoption or culture is a problem that is faced by many towns in the world, especially in Africa and other developing countries. Humphreys (1998) alluded to the fact that, delivery of services has a direct and immediate effect on the quality of the lives of the people in a given community. Poor services can make it difficult to attract business or industry to an area and it will also limit job opportunities for residents (Humphreys, 1998). Hence, as Besley and Ghatak (2007) indicate, improving public organisational performance is one of the biggest challenges worldwide.

Gwayi (2010) argues that mu Nzuve and Nyaega (2012) opined that Performance management and improvement is at the heart of strategic management because a lot of strategic thinking is geared towards defining and measuring performance. Awino (2011) asserts that for an organization to be successful it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization. Municipalities in South Africa face serious challenges in implementing Organisational performance options that will enhance existing structures in the sphere of local government points towards the need for strategies to improve Organisational performance. To date, there are limited studies that have formally investigated the causes of poor Organisational performance and the strategies that can be implemented to improve the Organisational performance in local authorities. The Rwandese Association of Local Government Authorities (RALGA) in 2010 reported on the factors affecting Organisational performance in local governments.

With certain autonomy power, the County is measured to enhance the increased demand from the communities for a more customer oriented and higher standard of both rural and urban services. The County Government of TransNzoia County, has the following thirteen (13) departments/ministries: office of the governor, human resource department, county public service board, Finance and Economic Planning, Lands, Housing and Physical Planning, Trade, Industry, Cooperative Development and Tourism, Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, Public Service Management, Public, Works, Roads and Transport, Water, Energy, Forestry and Natural Resources, Information, Communication and E-Government, Education, Youth Affairs, Culture and Social Services and Health Services. For effective County government performance aforementioned mandates, there creates need to employ strategic management adoption to ensure utmost value for the public (County Government of TransNzoia County Website, 2017).

The world is increasingly getting complex, and so are organizations. With multiple dynamic and competing factors coming into play, there is need to put in place effective strategic management plan to meet modern management challenges (Alukonya, 2021). To compete successfully in this environment, organizations continually need to improve their performance by reducing cost, innovating products and processes and improving quality, productivity and speed to market (Bryson et al.,2022). Proper strategic management adoption should provide a platform for all relevant stakeholders in project

identification, timely and adequate absorption of development funds to implementation of planned projects and programs (Chungyas, et al.,2022).

A number of studies on strategic management adoption in various organizations have been carried out in the past. On the international front (Almansoori, et al.,2023). who studied on influence of strategic management adoption in governments in Europe using a correlational research design noted that change is needed when environmental conditions change. In Africa the Rwandese Association of Local Government Authorities (RALGA) in 2010 reported on the factors affecting Performance in local governments. However, it did not empirically examine the strategies that can be adopted to improve Performance in local authorities. Locally a study by Njau (2001) on challenges of strategy implementation concluded that whereas some firms realized the need to change their strategy due to change in the competitive environment, they lacked finances and managerial empowerment to do so. This study therefore sought to examine the influence of strategic planning adoption on Performance of TransNzoia County.

2. STRATEGIC PLANNING ADOPTION ON ORGANISATIONAL PERFORMANCE

Strategic planning is an organization management activity that is used to set priorities, focus energy and resources to strengthen operations. Strategy planning according to McWilliams et al., (2006) is viewed as a critical way that the firms use to address the stakeholders to analyze their expectations. Strategic planning involves identification of most important options towards the realization of a practical vision (Bryson, 2015).

Strategic planning is also defined as organizational management activity that is used to set priorities, consolidate energy and resources, strengthen operations capability, ensure stakeholders and workers are working toward common goals, and assess and align organization's direction in with changing environment (David, 2011; Dyer, Godfrey, Jensen, & Bryce, 2016). A strategy is seen as the approach to be used step by step by an organization to most effectively accomplish its mission towards a practical vision. It is a set of procedures and tools designed to help leaders, managers and planners think and act strategically. In this study, strategic planning shall be measured by timely planning, organizational control systems, organizational competitive advantage and Organizational resource utilization.

Strategic planning is a process not done as a once off activity but as a continuous process. It helps stakeholders in an organization or a project determine what they intend to accomplish in a specified period of time (Barry, 2015). This ensures that employees and other stakeholders are working towards common goals that have established agreement around intended outcomes or results, assess and adjust the organizations direction in response to actions that shape and guide what an organization serves, what it does and why it does it, while focusing on the future (BSSI,2014).

Strategic planning thus enhances target attainment and thus organisational performance, for example, UN Agencies (UNA) drives focus through its engagement acceptance process which is also a central component of the organization risk management system. The process ensures that the organization only accepts projects that emphasize their strategic plan. Specifically, this assessment checks that new projects offer effective contributions to national capability, development and incorporate the three dimensions of sustainability, which are; sustainable project management, sustainable infrastructure and sustainable procurement. A case in point is where they ensure that all projects are screened and approved using minimum sustainability standards with higher sustainability targets negotiated wherever possible. It should be noted that strategic planning is not given the weight it deserves as an important aspect for ensuring transforming the lives of the people (Paul, 2015). In another study on sustainability, in India, rated the strategic planning in local government as moderately low primarily due to uncertainty regarding factors such as failure to get continuous support. It is important to note that the details of the strategy must be based on the whole spectrum of environmental, social and political conditions. It was noted that performance strategy created during the design phase with its complement of completion indicators are more than the norm in development projects around the world (IFAD, 2012). According to Schilder (2013), successful efforts, involve stakeholders support. Strategic plan development requires consideration and articulation of values and priorities; the plan should reflect views expressed by all those involved in the process.

According to Mulwa (2010), strategic planning concerns itself with vision, mission, goals and values of the organization, which the organization will serve, organization role in the community further concerned with resources needed – people, money expertise, relationships and facilities. Bryson (2015) observed that strategic planning is a technical approach that is, the planning team should be hybrid so that there is some assurance that both political and technical concerns are addressed. It fuses planning and decision making. County governments in Kenya face various challenges especially related to strategic

planning. For instance, there is evidence that there are no satisfactory resources availed to complete the necessary internal and external oversight and audits that are in county governments legislation (GoK, 2015). Second there is no guarantee that ordinary counties will be fully knowledgeable and able to act effectively in developing plans for effective organisational performance. Thirdly the county government programs are subject to cumbersome processes of coordination with other government agencies opening a loop hole for fraud and corruption. This is especially significant against broader efforts to decentralization. Further it will be necessary to develop procedures for effective cost planning in support of project implementation as it is necessary to address the politicized nature of the County funds, in order to ensure project completion regardless of electoral results. In the prevailing scenarios County funds are dispersed to various projects without due reference to neither Strategic plans nor the time frame of the project. Nyandemo (2010) argues that the repairs maintenance, rehabilitations are given equal chances like a planned and approved project depending on the political environment and availability of funds therefore. There is need to consider the influence of a Strategic plan to further funding. This is not given attention it deserves before discernment of the funds, therefore significantly affects the completion of the project. The researcher suggests that strategic planning as an approach should be leveraged upon to enhance sustainability in project management since much of its benefits can be attested for.

A significant number of recent investigations suggest that an efficient and effective strategic planning system can enhance organisational performance. On the average, organizations that plan outperform those that do not. In one of such studies by Rhyme (2013) on influence of strategic planning systems on financial performance, it can be concluded, organizations with strategic planning systems more closely resembling strategic management theory were found to “exhibit superior long-term financial performance both relative to their industry and absolute terms”. The major studies of strategic management carried out in Nigeria by Oyedijo & Akinlabi (2004 & 2008) and Akingbade (2007) have found support for the strategic planning and corporate performance hypothesis. For instance, their studies revealed that SMEs corporate financial performance tends to increase with a unit increase in the level of practice of strategic planning. The higher the overall level of strategic management adoption by SMEs, the higher the financial performance of the SMEs expressed in terms of earnings per share, profit before tax, return on capital employed, net asset, current or working capital ratio, increase in relative market share, continuing addition of new products and products lines, and total deposits. For all the financial performance indicators used, performance tended to increase significantly as the level (or degree of sophistication) of strategic management increased.

With successful strategic management adoption means that the organisations will be able to achieve its objectives in a timely and in competitiveness since it is concerned with the overall productivity in an organization in terms of stock turnover, customers, profitability and market share. The concept of organizational performance is core to businesses because the major objective of businesses is to make profits. Iravo et. al., (2013) state that one of the important questions in business has been why some organizations succeed and why others fail and this has influenced a study on the drivers of organizational performance.

Organizational performance is concerned with the overall productivity in an organization in terms of stock turnover, customers, profitability and market share. The concept of organizational performance is core to businesses because the major objective of businesses is to make profits. Iravo et. al., (2013) state that one of the important questions in business has been why some organizations succeed and why others fail and this has influenced a study on the drivers of organizational performance. Fwaya (2006) views performance as a formula for the assessment of the functioning of an organization under certain parameters such as productivity, employee’ morale and effectiveness. Nzuve and Nyaega (2012) opined that Performance management and improvement is at the heart of strategic management because a lot of strategic thinking is geared towards defining and measuring performance. Awino (2011) asserts that for an organization to be successful it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization. Odhiambo (2009) identified three approaches to performance in an organization which are the goal approach, which states that an organization pursues definite identifiable goals. This approach describes performance in terms of the attainment of these goals. The second approach is the systems resource approach which defines performance as a relationship between an organization and its environment. This concept defines performance according to an organization’s ability to secure the limited and valued resources in the environment. The third approach is the process perspective which defines performance in terms of the behaviour of the human resource of an organization (Waiganjo et. al., 2012). Kiragu (2005) highlights performance in terms of four perspectives which are the financial, customer, internal processes and innovativeness. The financial perspective identifies the key financial drivers of enhancing performance which are profit margin, asset turnover, leverage, cash flow, and working capital (Odhuno and Wadongo, 2010).

Odhiambo (2009) states that the first approach describes performance in terms of the attainment of these goals. The second approach is the systems resource approach which defines performance as a relationship between an organization and its environment. This concept defines performance according to an organization's ability to secure the limited and valued resources in the environment. The third approach is the process perspective which defines performance in terms of the behaviour of the human resource of an organization (Waiganjo et. al., 2012). Kiragu (2005) highlights performance in terms of four perspectives which are the financial, customer, internal processes and innovativeness. The financial perspective identifies the key financial drivers of enhancing performance which are profit margin, asset turnover, leverage, cash flow, and working capital (Odhuno and Wadongo, 2010). The customer focus describes performance in terms of brand image, customer satisfaction, and customer retention and customer profitability. Internal processes involve the efficiency of all the systems in the organization while innovativeness is concerned with the ease with which a firm is able to adapt to changing conditions.

3. METHOD

This study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population for the study was comprised of heads of departments in the county government of TransNzoia. The study worked with entire population which is census. Data collection instrument was questionnaire and other information relevant to the study. Both primary and secondary data was collected. The research instrument was pretested at Uasin Gishu County so as not to interfere with the study sample. The findings of the pilot study was used to improve the data collection instruments. The data was reduced, organized, coded, edited, classified using a table and analysed to bring out the meaning under each of the factors. Once data is collected, it was crosschecked and verified for errors, completeness and consistency. It was then be coded, entered and analysed descriptively using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SSPS 23). Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between variables in the study hypotheses. ANOVA multiple linear regression analysis was adopted computed to determine the statistical relationship between the independent variable and the dependent.

4. DISCUSSIONS

The first specific objective of the study was to examine the influence of strategic planning adoption on Performance of TransNzoia County. The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on statements relating to the influence of strategic planning adoption on Performance of TransNzoia County. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in Table 4.1.

From the results, the respondents agreed that employees and other stakeholders should work towards common goals that have established agreement around intended outcomes or results. This is supported by a mean of 3.941 (std. dv = 0.851). In addition, as shown by a mean of 4.892 (std. dv = 0.785), the respondents agreed that strategic plan development requires consideration and articulation of values and priorities; the plan should reflect views expressed by all those involved in the process.

Further, the respondents agreed that strategic planning concerns itself with vision, mission, goals and values of the organization, which the organization will serve, organization role in the community further concerned with resources needed people, money expertise, relationships and facilities. This is shown by a mean of 3.861 (std. dv = 0.873).

The respondents also agreed that the success of any firm is predicated on the strategic planning. This is shown by a mean of 3.816 (std. dv = 0.844). With a mean of 3.513 (std. dv = 0.763), the respondents agreed that the county government should assess and adjust the organizations direction in response to actions that shape and guide what an organization serves, what it does and why it does it, while focusing on the future. Further, the respondents agreed that efficient and effective strategic planning system can enhance organizational performance. This is shown by a mean of 3.751 (std. dv = 0.866).

Table 4.1: Influence of Strategic Planning Adoption on Performance of TransNzoia County;

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Employees and other stakeholders should work towards common goals that have established agreement around intended outcomes or results.	3.941	0.851
Strategic plan development requires consideration and articulation of values and priorities; the plan should reflect views expressed by all those involved in the process	4.892	0.785

Strategic planning concerns itself with vision, mission, goals and values of the organization, which the organization will serve, organization role in the community further concerned with resources needed people, money expertise, relationships and facilities	3.861	0.853
The success of any firm is predicated on the strategic planning	3.816	0.844
The county government should assess and adjust the organizations direction in response to actions that shape and guide what an organization serves, what it does and why it does it, while focusing on the future	3.513	0.763
Efficient and effective strategic planning system can enhance organizational performance	3.751	0.866
Aggregate	3.902	0.895

4.2. Performance of TransNzoia County, Kenya.

The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on various statements relating to the effect of Performance of TransNzoia County. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in table 4.2.

From the results, the respondents agreed that with successful strategic management adoption means that the firms will be able to achieve its objectives in a timely and in competitiveness since it is concerned with the overall productivity in an organization in terms of stock turnover, customers, profitability and market shares. This is supported by a mean of 4.281 (std. dv = 0.957). In addition, as shown by a mean of 3.978 (std. dv = 0.841), the respondents agreed that A suitable strategies should assist the management team to achieve high performance in the organization. This is shown by a mean of 3.823 (std. dv = 0.752). The respondents also agreed that Inclusion of stakeholders in the top management team only enhances firm performance if it brings about a long-term orientation among management. This is shown by a mean of 3.812 (std. dv = 0.843). With a mean of 3.743 (std. dv = 0.925), the respondents agreed that Organizational performance should relate to how successfully an organized group of people with a particular purpose of commitment perform a function to achieve great results measured in terms of the value delivered to customers. The respondent also agreed that the concept of organizational performance is core to businesses because the major objective of businesses is to make profits through customer satisfaction e.t.c. This is shown by a mean of 3.961 (std. dv = 0.911).

Table 4.2: Performance of TransNzoia County, Kenya.

	Mean	Std. Deviation
With successful strategic management adoption means that the firms will be able to achieve its objectives in a timely and in competitiveness since it is concerned with the overall productivity in an organization in terms of stock turnover, customers, profitability and market share	4.281	0.957
A suitable strategies should assist the management team to achieve high performance in the organization	3.978	0.841
Inclusion of stakeholders in the top management team only enhances firm performance if it brings about a long-term orientation among management	3.823	0.752
For a firm to be successful it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization	3.812	0.843
Organizational performance should relate to how successfully an organized group of people with a particular purpose of commitment perform a function to achieve great results measured in terms of the value delivered to customers.	3.743	0.925
The concept of organizational performance is core to businesses because the major objective of businesses is to make profits through customer satisfaction e.t.c	3.961	0.911
Aggregate	3.997	0.841

4.3 Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics in the current study focused on correlation and regression analysis. Correlation analysis was used to determine the strength of the relationship while regression analysis was used to determine the relationship between dependent variable (Performance of TransNzoia County, Kenya and the independent variable (strategic planning adoption).

4.3.1 Correlation Analysis

The present study used Pearson correlation analysis to determine the strength of association between independent variables (strategic planning adoption) and the dependent variable (Performance of TransNzoia County, Kenya) dependent variable. Pearson correlation coefficient range between zero and one, where by the strength of association increase with increase in the value of the correlation coefficients. The current study employed Taylor (2018) correlation coefficient ratings where by 0.80 to 1.00 depicts a very strong relationship, 0.60 to 0.79 depicts strong, 0.40 to 0.59 depicts moderate, 0.20 to 0.39 depicts weak.

Table 4.3: Correlation Coefficients

	Performance of TransNzoia County		Strategic planning adoption	
Performance of TransNzoia County	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	39		
Strategic planning adoption	Pearson Correlation	.807**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002		
	N	39	39	

From the results, there was a very strong relationship between strategic planning adoption and Performance of TransNzoia County. ($r = 0.807$, p value = 0.002). The relationship was significant since the p value 0.002 was less than 0.05 (significant level).

4.3.2 Regression Analysis

Multivariate regression analysis was used to assess the relationship between independent variables (strategic planning adoption) and the dependent variable (Performance of TransNzoia County).

Table 4.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.899	.731	.726	.324122

a. Predictors: (Constant), Strategic Planning Adoption

The model summary was used to explain the variation in the dependent variable that could be explained by the independent variables. The r-squared for the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable was 0.731. This implied that 73.1% of the variation in the dependent variable (Performance of TransNzoia County) could be explained by independent variables (strategic planning adoption).

Table 4.5: Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	33.351	1	3.241	42.17	.000 ^b
	Residual	6.471	38	.039		
	Total	39.722	39			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of TransNzoia County

b. Predictors: (Constant), strategic planning adoption

The ANOVA was used to determine whether the model was a good fit for the data. F calculated was 42.17 while the F critical was 2.013. The p value was 0.000. Since the F-calculated was greater than the F-critical and the p value 0.000 was less than 0.05, the model was considered as a good fit for the data. Therefore, the model can be used to predict the influence of strategic planning adoption on Performance of TransNzoia County.

Table 4.6: Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	0.559	0.032		4.434	0.000
	Strategic planning adoption	0.613	0.067	0.335	3.502	0.000

a. **Dependent Variable:** Performance of TransNzoia County.

The regression model was as follows:

$$Y = 0.559 + 0.613X_1$$

According to the results, strategic planning adoption has a significant effect on Performance of TransNzoia County. $\beta_1=0.613$, p value= 0.000). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.004 was less than the significant level of 0.05.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The first specific objective of the study was to examine the influence of strategic planning adoption on Performance of TransNzoia County. The findings revealed that employees and other stakeholders should work towards common goals that have established agreement around intended outcomes or results and that strategic plan development requires consideration and articulation of values and priorities; the plan should reflect views expressed by all those involved in the process. Further, the findings indicated that strategic planning concerns itself with vision, mission, goals and values of the organization, which the organization will serve, organization role in the community further concerned with resources needed people, money expertise, relationships and facilities. The findings also showed that the success of any firm is predicated on the strategic planning and that the county government should assess and adjust the organizations direction in response to actions that shape and guide what an organization serves, what it does and why it does it, while focusing on the future as efficient and effective strategic planning system can enhance organizational performance. Based on the findings, the study concluded that strategic planning adoption has a significant effect on Performance of TransNzoia County. $\beta_1=0.613$, p value= 0.000). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.004 was less than the significant level of 0.05. The study came up with the following recommendations; the management of the county government should come up with Strategic plan that meets the county government's requirements in consideration and articulation of values and priorities reflecting the views expressed by all stakeholders involved in the process. The adoption process should involve the strategic vision, mission, goals and values of the organization.

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